

Complex Probabilities in Free Particle Quantum Mechanics Part 2

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Oct. 21, 2025

In Part 1, we focused on the classical probability statement $1 = P(\text{reflect}) + P(\text{refract})$ for one dimensional reflection-refraction of a photon at an n_1 - n_2 junction (index of refraction). We argued that the form $\exp(ipx)$ exists as part of $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ which is a Lorentz invariant free particle probability which allows for equal product probabilities for any (e_i, e_j) energy and (p_i, p_j) momentum vector pairs which conserve energy and momentum with (e_1, e_2) , (p_1, p_2) . Furthermore, it is linked with conservation of energy and momentum.

In other words there is an inherent probability present in Newtonian free particle mechanics, but this probability is different from classical probability in that it is a property of the particle itself and not just the interaction. A coin or die yields an unpredictable outcome due to the interaction not being influenced by the number on the die or face of the coin. A particle described by $\exp(ipx)$ has a probability to interact with either both slits of a 2-slit apparatus if their separation is about $\hbar/|p|$. This suggests that there is a probabilistic physical feature in space linked to a particle having momentum. Otherwise, there should be no 2-slit interference. This probability is linked with conservation of momentum. In Part 1, we tried to argue that $\exp(ipx)$, by containing x , is also linked with probability in space.

In this note, we argue that the probability linked with the particle, which controls the values of $P(\text{reflect})$ and $P(\text{refract})$ has properties beyond just the wavelength. A single photon which happens to reflect from an n_1 - n_2 junction with $n_1 < n_2$ receives a phase shift of $\exp(i \cdot 3.14) = -1$. This is needed in order to deal with flux issues. Even though both $n_1 < n_2$ and $n_2 < n_1$ lead to $1 = P(\text{reflect}) + P(\text{refract})$, only $n_1 < n_2$ causes a reflected photon to pick up a phase. The interaction at the n_1 - n_2 junction being probabilistic in the particle itself leads to an almost sensing of the two possible outcomes during the interaction and the balance equations which have mixed time terms (as we show). This is different from a stochastic reaction which simply takes a particle and stochastically hits it one way or the other. The reflected particle is not independent of the refracted one, even though only one is produced in any given interaction. This is because the probability in the interaction is associated with the particle and not the interaction. Even though a photon is either reflected or refracted, there must be some physical mechanism linked with the particle which ensures that $P(\text{reflect})$ and $P(\text{refract})$ are correct and that there are no flux violations in the two equations which create $1 = P(\text{reflect}) + P(\text{refract})$.

Photon Reflection-Refraction

One dimensional photon reflection-refraction at an n_1 - n_2 index of refraction junction is based on the classical equation:

$$1 = P(\text{reflect}) + P(\text{refract}) \quad ((1))$$

This holds for both $n_1 < n_2$ and $n_2 > n_1$. We argued in Part 1, that there is an internal probability present which allows one to break ((1)) into two equations. This internal probability is linked with

dynamics (i.e. p) as well as fluxes. Fluxes are linked to speed and not just actual particle conservation. We argued in Part 1, that for two body elastic Newtonian scattering, one may introduce a Lorentz invariant probability $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ which ensured that any (e_i, e_j) energy and (p_i, p_j) momentum vector product probabilities have the same value as that for (e_1, e_2) and (p_1, p_2) . The probability is complex because any free particle carries the same real value weight. Nevertheless, one may have fluxes of free particles which do not have the same value. It seems this flux value is then important when considering $\exp(ipx)$.

We argued in Part 1, that $\exp(ipx)$ governs the value of probability in the n_1 - n_2 reflection-refraction problem. It is known that an $\exp(ipx)$ particle interacts with both slits in a 2-slit apparatus which is non-classical behaviour. We argue that there must be a stochastic property, yet physical at the same time, in space linked with a particle having a p . In the n_1 - n_2 interaction, one sees that matters are more complicated, because the probability $\exp(ipx)$ with weights linked to flux actually determines $P(\text{reflect})$ and $P(\text{refract})$. In other words, the stochasticity is linked with the particle and not the interaction, although properties of the interaction influence how the stochasticity must "behave". $\exp(ipx)$ is stochastic, but is linked to deterministic conservation of energy. We argue here that it may take on a phase $+1$ or -1 which is also linked to a deterministic result associated with fluxes.

Flux Issues in 1-D Reflection-Refraction

It is possible to write ((1)) in terms of dynamic variables, i.e.

$$AA/c = BB/c + CC/c_2 \quad ((2))$$

Here AA , BB and CC are the fluxes of the incident, reflected and refracted, c is the speed of light in $n_1=1$ and c_2 , in n_2 . We argued in Part 1, that one may break ((2)) into two equations:

$$(A+B) = C \quad \text{and} \quad p(A-B) = p_2 C \quad ((3))$$

where $E=pc$ and E is the same for the incident, reflected and refracted photon.

((3)) then follows from:

$$A\exp(ipx) + B\exp(-ipx) = C\exp(ip_2x) \quad \text{and} \quad pA\exp(ipx) - pB\exp(-ipx) = Cp_2 \exp(ip_2x) \quad \text{at } x=0 \quad ((4))$$

There is continuity of $\exp(ipx)$ s for the incident, reflected and refracted photons (events which occur at different times) as well as continuity of the first derivative d/dx at $x=0$. The same equations hold for both $n_1 < n_2$ and $n_1 > n_2$. In fact, one may simply solve and find B and C in terms of A . As is well known, B is negative for $n_1 < n_2$. This is not simply a math result, but a physical one. $\exp(ipx)$ is linked with $\hbar p/|p|$ which is physical (in terms of interactions), but a phase of $-1 = \exp(i 3.14)$ may result. This is experimentally verifiable as a photon which reflects from air to glass will interfere with one that is moving in the same direction, but did not reflect, i.e. did not pick up the -1 phase. (Physically, an experiment (as is well known) using two glass plates with one at angle to the other may be performed to verify this. One photon reflects off

glass once (-1), and the other twice (-1*-1) and so the two interfere based on the phase picked up by $\exp(ipx)$ passing through the air between the glass plates (back and forth).

If a single photon reaches an n_1 - n_2 junction, with $n_1 < n_2$ and happens to reflect, it will acquire the $-1 = \exp(i 3.14)$ phase. This suggests that the result of reflection is not a random feature of the interaction, but that in this interaction, there is a “sensing” of the two possibilities, reflection and refraction, and also the notion that $c_2 < c_1$ which affects flux. In fact, the phase -1 only occurs if $n_1 < n_2$ because if one considers $A+B=C$, sets $A=1$ and argues that for $n_1 < n_2$ that $C < A$ (where $CC = \text{flux}$) then B must be negative. We note that AA/c is the incident particle number and CC/c_2 refracted particle number. Given that

$$AA/c > CC/c_2 \text{ and } c_2 < c_1 \quad AA > CC \quad c/c_2 \text{ so } A > C \quad ((5))$$

This may only be enforced in $A+B = C$ by B being negative, i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ acquiring a phase. Thus, the stochasticity of $\exp(ipx)$ which appears in ((3)) and ((4)), which governs the outcome, is able to sense different outcomes and create a physical property linked to the phase -1. This must be a physical property because otherwise a photon which reflects from glass would not interfere with one that is moving in the same direction, but with no phase shift from reflection. The mixing of different time events implied by ((3)) and ((4)) seems to be sampled or sensed already in the interaction in order that a reflected photon acquire its phase.

Thus, classical probabilistic equations, such as ((1)) involve events that occur at different times as we stressed in Part 1. Here we argue that there may already be a sensing of the different time events at the level of the interaction, otherwise it would not be clear how a reflected photon ($n_1 < n_2$) would know that it should acquire a phase. It is not simply a matter of breaking ((1)) into two equations (which holds for $n_1 < n_2$ and $n_2 < n_1$), but it seems to be the case that a physical attribute (phase $-1 = \exp(i 3.14)$) is obtained by a reflected photon in a single incident to reflected photon interaction for $n_1 < n_2$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that even though probability statements $1 = P(\text{reflect}) + P(\text{refract})$ ((6)) represent events that occur at different times, the $\exp(ipx)$ formalism used in Part 1, to create ((6)) from two continuity equations ((3)) and ((4)) seems to rest with probability being associated with a particle. As a result, we argue that a single incident photon which happens to reflect from an n_1 - n_2 junction (with $n_1 < n_2$) senses that there are two outcomes and that $C < A$ and so acquires a physical phase of $-1 = \exp(i 3.14)$. We already argued in Part 1, that it is the probabilistic $\exp(ipx)$ associated with conservation of momentum which ensures the values of $P(\text{reflect})$ and $P(\text{refract})$ without one paying attention to whether B is negative or not, but the case that B may acquire a phase of $-1 = \exp(i 3.14)$ suggests that an interaction senses the probabilistic outcomes and their conservation issues including momentum (which is key to $\exp(ipx)$), but even flux considerations which accounts for why B is negative. Furthermore, conservation of momentum is linked with a physical wavelength in $\exp(ipx)$ and the phase $-1 = \exp(i 3.14)$ is also physical as experiments show that a photon, reflected from glass) interferes with one not reflected and moving in the same direction. This appears to be very different from say the toss of a coin.

